

CubeOS: Design and Implementation of a General-Purpose TPCM Operating System

Jun Hu, Changxiang Shen, and Jin Zhou

Abstract—As the core component of Autonomous Trusted Computing (ATC) architecture, Trusted Platform Control Module (TPCM) constructs security monitoring processes on-demand through its own operating system, achieving dynamic collaboration of multiple security mechanisms. Herein, we designed a general-purpose TPCM operating system CubeOS, guided by four fundamental design principles. Based on abstract representations of security monitoring processes first proposed in this work, we designed a three-layered architecture for CubeOS, and defined standardized TPCM operating system interfaces, consisting of function APIs and configuration data interfaces. As the secure collaboration system, CubeOS provides trusted cryptographic services for the entire system. CubeOS provides standardized adaptation methods to interact with security mechanisms external to TPCM, thus enabling compatibility with diverse security mechanisms. Furthermore, a standardized scheme was proposed to facilitate collaboration among multiple security mechanisms. Additionally, the primary security threats to CubeOS were analyzed by Communicating Sequential Processes (CSP). As an implementation of CubeOS, we developed cubeos-1.5 in an isolated and minimalistic manner in the Linux environment, evaluated the performance of cubeos-1.5 by conducting a series of performance tests, and enabled adaptation for cubeos-1.5 to external security mechanisms. In a data security assurance scenario, we demonstrated a verifying example of realizing security monitoring processes by employing cubeos-1.5. Our study shows that CubeOS can be served as a cross-platform general-purpose operating system across various TPCM platforms, and provides security assurance for data circulation and use in scenarios such as the industrial internet, trusted data spaces, and AI security applications.

Index Terms—Autonomous Trusted Computing (ATC), Trusted Platform Control Module (TPCM), TPCM operating system, security mechanism collaboration, cross-platform security.

1 INTRODUCTION

THE primary and pressing challenge in current cybersecurity is to achieve precise usage control over data circulation and transaction processes. As isolated security mechanisms are difficult to meet these demands, great efforts have been stimulated on the approaches of ensuring cybersecurity through dynamic collaboration among multiple security mechanisms in recent years. Models like ABAC [1], UCON [2], Activity control [3] and so forth proposed strengthening access controls by evaluating dynamic and

contextual factors, while they failed effectively practiced from concept, primarily because of a lack of implementation frameworks. Architecturally, although the Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) [4] supported multiple security mechanism collaboration through dynamic trust evaluation, its trust model cannot accurately represent the complex trust relationships in real-world environment, thus failing to meet the needs of data circulation and transaction. At the hardware level, Trusted Platform Module (TPM) [5] provided cryptographic functions, and Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) [6] ensured hardware protections. However, both their applications faced bottlenecks such as “lack of trusted service orchestration mechanism” and “insufficient cross platform interoperability”. [7].

Therefore, it necessitates the exploration of new ways to realize the precise usage control over data circulation and transaction processes. Shen et al. proposed the Autonomous Trusted Computing (ATC), an innovative security framework [8]–[10]. In this architecture, the host’s traditional system serves as the computing component, while an independent security component is designed to enable dynamic collaboration among multiple security mechanisms. This security component is built in a trusted manner and shields against external threats through hardware and/or software isolation. Security components across different hosts communicate with the security management center via a dedicated network, which is either independent or logically isolated from the standard network using cryptographic mechanisms.

The overall ATC architecture is illustrated in Figure 1, in which the security component is typically implemented by Trusted Platform Control Module (TPCM) [11]. TPCM connects the local system bus, security management center, and Trusted Cryptographic Module (TCM) [12] or Trusted Platform Module (TPM) [13]. With the own operating system, TPCM can construct multiple security monitoring processes as needed and run them in parallel. The combination of these processes mainly constitutes the Trust Software Base (TSB) [14], which is defined as a basic component of ATC architecture and exert dynamic security management functions. As the basic unit for implementing dynamic collaboration of security mechanisms, the security monitoring process also provides support for trusted cryptographic functionality and cross-node security collaboration. The implementation of security monitoring process is divided into two phases: construction and execution. In the construction

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Fig. 1. Architecture of autonomous trusted computing.

phase, data transmission computing paths are constructed, and connect audit interfaces and policy interfaces of different security mechanisms. In the execution phase, audit information is transmitted along the data path, meanwhile, the security situation is analyzed, and security policies are generated. Finally, the security policies are output to the security mechanism.

It is important to note that although the ATC architecture can be implemented using TEE and TPM/TCM, TPCM is generally introduced in the ATC architecture to maintain the independence of the security component and to enhance the security robustness of the system. Over the past decade, researchers have explored various implementation method of TPCM, including USB Key mode [15], bus plug-in card mode [16], BMC board mode [17], and specialized CPU core mode [18]. Additionally, technologies such as TEE can also provide a simplified version of TPCM.

However, the operating systems for these TPCMs [19] were developed separately, each defining its own interfaces. This heterogeneity makes these TPCM operating systems difficult to port across different platforms and adapt to various security mechanisms. It significantly impedes the promotion of autonomous trusted computing. Consequently, designing and implementing a general-purpose TPCM operating system for the standardized development of security monitoring processes is an urgent demand for advancing autonomous trusted computing.

To address this challenge, there exist four key issues: (1) How to design a multi-layer TPCM operating system architecture for easy porting to different TPCM environments. (2) How to design standardized interfaces to support the construction and execution of security monitoring processes in a general manner. (3) How to establish standardized adaptation methods for TPCM interacting with

external security mechanisms to ensure compatibility. (4) How to propose a standardized development methodology for dynamic collaboration of multiple security mechanisms, thereby lowering the barrier for securing data circulation.

Herein, we designed a general-purpose TPCM operating system CubeOS. We established four fundamental design principles for CubeOS. Based on five basic objects as abstract representations of security monitoring processes, we designed a three-layered architecture for CubeOS, and defined standardized TPCM operating system interfaces, consisting of function APIs and configuration data interfaces. We provided trusted cryptographic services for the entire system. We provided standardized adaptation methods to interact with security mechanisms external to the TPCM. Furthermore, we proposed a standardized development scheme for dynamic collaboration of multiple security mechanisms. Additionally, we analyzed the primary security threats to CubeOS by using CSP. As an implementation of CubeOS, we developed cubeos-1.5 in the Linux environment, evaluated the performance of cubeos-1.5 by conducting a series of performance tests, and enabled adaptation to various types of security mechanisms. In an AI data security assurance scenario, we employed cubeos-1.5 to construct and run security monitoring process, and demonstrated a verifying example of realizing the precise usage control over data circulation and transaction processes. Our work provides comprehensive support for TPCM utilization, and its results can be widely used in cloud computing, Internet of Things (IoT), big data, industrial internet and other scenarios.

2 DESIGN OF A GENERAL-PURPOSE TPCM OPERATING SYSTEM CUBEOS

2.1 The design principle of CubeOS

Drawing from the design philosophy of Unix systems [20], we proposed design principles to meet the requirements of on-demand implementation of security monitoring process, and used these principles as guidance throughout the entire CubeOS design process.

The principle of modularity and the single purpose. Use multiple relatively independent and functionally singular modules to construct the security monitoring processes, with each module designed for single purpose. This principle aims to enhance the maintainability and reusability of the security monitoring mechanism, while maintaining the core stability of the TPCM operating system.

The principle of composition. Enable different modules of the security monitoring process to achieve functional composition through well-defined interfaces, thereby completing complex monitoring functions. This principle aims to reduce the difficulty of implementing the security monitoring process and enhance the flexibility and reusability of module usage.

The principle of uniform abstraction. Construct and run the security monitoring processes through a unified set of object operations. This principle aims to provide a transparent implementation method for the security monitoring process, supporting the migration of the security monitoring process across different TPCM environments and facilitating adaptation of the security monitoring process to various security mechanisms.

The principle of mechanism-policy separation. Implement the mechanism and policy of the security monitoring process separately. A general-purpose TPCM operating system should provide the mechanisms to build the security monitoring process, while developers provide customized policies to determine how these mechanisms are used. This principle aims to enable developers to control and design flexibly while maintaining the generality and stability of the system.

2.2 Abstract expression of security monitoring processes in CubeOS

Guided by the design principles of CubeOS, we designed five basic objects to represent the construction and execution of security monitoring processes. These five objects are **record**, **message**, **module**, **channel**, and **route**. Records and messages are employed to represent the monitoring data flow in execution phase, while modules, channels, and routes are used to construct the data transmission and computation paths in the construction phase, serving as the data paths for the monitoring data flow.

Record is used to represent the data related to security monitoring processes. In CubeOS, records are data characterized by a predefined structure, and their format is specified by a tuple of (type, subtype). Records can be represented in forms such as memory data structures, binary packages, and JSON strings to accommodate the needs of the transmission and processing of data. In addition, CubeOS provides an in-memory record database to store

and share the computation results of different security monitoring processes. Figure 2a shows the conversion process of records.

Message serves as carriers for records to support the transmission of monitoring data. In CubeOS, a message comprises a header, a record area, and an extension area, as shown in Figure 2b. The header stores the relevant data and transmission attributes. The record area is a set of records defined in the header, which are the primary transmission payload. The extension area consists of records that carry their own definitions, allowing the security monitoring process to add data during the execution phase.

Module acts as a computational unit in the security monitoring processes. Figure 2c illustrates the internal structure of the module. Module comprises one or more computational logic fragments, which are encapsulated in different message processing functions to complete discrete security monitoring tasks. Module uses messages as both input and output. Input messages in different formats can activate different message processing functions, enabling the conversion from the data transmission to the data computation. After the computation, the output message is generated, and the security monitoring process returns to the data transmission.

Channel is the data endpoint for CubeOS to connect with external security mechanisms. TPCM provides three external interfaces: a bus interface for interacting with system security mechanisms, a device interface for accessing TCM, and a network interface for communicating with other TPCMs. CubeOS provides bus channels, device channels, and network channels for these three interfaces, respectively. To meet the parallel operation requirements of security monitoring processes, CubeOS sets up read/write buffer areas in channels to support non-blocking communication. Figure 2d shows the data flow transformation in channels.

Route is the description of the propagation path of messages in CubeOS. Route includes the definition, matching rules, and transmission paths, as shown in Figure 2e. Route specifies the transmission path of message that conforms to matching rules, which is composed of a series of modules.

Figure 2f illustrates the way in which route constructs the message transmission path. Route can be categorized into two types: the primary route and the auxiliary route. The primary route specifies the backbone of the message transmission path. The auxiliary route taps into the primary route via a pointcut, enabling auxiliary functions such as cryptographic support and secure collaboration without impacting on the primary data flow. There are two implementation methods for auxiliary route: duplication (D) and interception (I). Duplication involves copying messages from a pointcut in primary route for processing. Interception involves intercepting messages at a pointcut in the primary route, processing in the auxiliary route, and then returning to the pointcut to recover message transmission in the primary route.

Based on these five objects, we can design abstract expressions of security monitoring processes in CubeOS, as shown in Figure 2g. As the computation part of security monitoring processes, modules can be divided into different types according to their functions, such as adaptation modules, management modules, and general modules. Routes

Fig. 2. From basic objects to the implementation of the security monitoring process in CubeOS.

TABLE 1
Classifications and functions of upper-layer interfaces in CubeOS.

Type	Classification	Interface functions
Configuration data interface	record configuration	Define record (format, key elements, and (type, subtype) identifier)
	Module configuration	Set module name, binary, and initialization parameters
	Route configuration	Define routes and specify pointcuts
functional API	Basic function API	Allocate/free memory, operate string/binary data, call crypt algorithms.
	Record processing API	Operate record (create, serialize, deserialize, compare, clone, and update)
	In-memory database API	Operate In-memory database (CRUD, query, index).
	Message processing API	Operate message (create, read, write, serialize, deserialize, security services (encrypt, sign), release.
	Module operation API	Send/receive messages and trigger events.
	Channel read/write API	Operate channel (read, write, lookup buffer, and reset channel reset.

connect different types of modules to construct a data path of security monitoring processes. During the execution of security monitoring processes, messages carry records along routes to generate a data flow for security monitoring. Different security monitoring processes can store and share data via an in-memory database, and collaborate through shared data. These expressions satisfy the design principles of CubeOS, enabling us to design CubeOS in a generalized way.

2.3 The three-layered architecture design of CubeOS

Based on the abstract expression of security monitoring processes, we designed a three-layered architecture for CubeOS, as illustrated in Figure 3. CubeOS consists of three layers: the bottom layer, the core layer, and the upper layer. The bottom layer provides hardware-level support such as CPU resources, storage resources, and TPCM external communication. The core layer provides functional support for the construction and execution of security monitoring processes in a platform-independent manner. The upper layer is a collection of basic objects, where modules, channels and routes construct security monitoring processes, while records and messages are generated during the execution of security processes, forming a monitoring data flow.

The bottom layer comprises five components: computing resource allocator, storage space allocator, system bus driver, TCM device driver, and network driver. Computing resource allocator and storage space allocator are utilized to request CPU time and storage space from TPCM hardware to support the execution of CubeOS. The system bus driver, TCM device driver, and network driver are employed to support the connection between CubeOS and external security mechanisms of TPCM.

The core layer comprises core data structures, functional libraries, core execution entities, and upper-layer interfaces. Core data structures provide data structures for basic object definition, management and execution. Functional libraries support the management and operation of basic objects. Core execution entities are utilized to execute management functions of the CubeOS core layer. Upper-layer interfaces provide interfaces for the management and operation of basic objects to the upper layer.

Upper-layer interfaces are the most critical part for enabling generalization in CubeOS, just as the POSIX standard does for Unix, which needs to be clearly defined in the design process. Upper-layer interfaces of CubeOS can be divided into two types: configuration data interface and

functional API. Configuration data interfaces are used to set monitoring policies of CubeOS during the initialization to construct security monitoring processes. Functional APIs provide function call interfaces for modules. Table 1 presents the functions of upper-layer interfaces of CubeOS.

The upper layer is a collection of five basic objects to support the construction and execution of security monitoring processes. The specific procedure is outlined in Figure 2g. These security monitoring processes mainly achieve the following functions: (1) **Dynamic security collaboration.** Obtains audit information through the security monitoring process, analyzes the system's trusted state, updates security policies based on the trusted state, deploys and implements them, and finally forms a dynamic protection domain that changes with the attributes of the protected entity. (2) **Trusted cryptography service.** Provides trusted cryptography service such as trusted measurement, trusted reporting, and trusted binding with TCM supporting. (3) **Remote security collaboration service.** Used to apply for remote node security mechanism to cooperate with local nodes for secure collaboration, or to respond to secure collaboration requests from remote nodes to local node security mechanisms.

From the design, it is evident that CubeOS is a special operating system dedicated to TPCM, which is significantly different from conventional general-purpose operating systems. To clarify this distinction, Table 2 presents a comparison between CubeOS and conventional general-purpose operating systems.

Notably, the ATC framework, with CubeOS as its core component, differs from the conventional TEE-based security co-processing systems. Therefore, we select OP-TEE, a widely adopted open-source TEE solution, as a baseline for a systematic comparison with CubeOS.

Table 3 compares the two architectures across seven key aspects, highlighting their fundamental differences in design philosophy. Typically, conventional TEE architectures focus on providing isolated execution environments for specific security-critical tasks. In contrast, CubeOS abstracts trusted security management into a unified framework that orchestrates diverse security mechanisms (including isolation, access control, and encryption) in a cohesive manner. This design enables CubeOS to integrate and coordinate diverse security mechanisms—including those leveraging TEE technologies—thereby establishing a more open, compatible, and extensible security assurance framework.

Fig. 3. The three-layered architecture of CubeOS.

TABLE 2
Comparison between CubeOS and conventional general-purpose operating systems and CubeOS.

Comparison Content	CubeOS	Conventional general-purpose operating system
Design Objectives	Orchestrate composable security monitoring processes on the TPCM	Manage and abstract hardware resources (CPU, memory, I/O) for applications
Fundamental Abstractions	Record, Message, Module, Channel, Route	Process & IPC, File, Socket, Device Driver
Deployment Model	Module loading, configuration input, monitoring process construction	Application installation, service configuration, user configuration management
Execution Model	Event-driven monitoring, Automated security analysis and policy update	Persistent system services, User-driven applications
Layered Architecture	Three layers: TPCM-dependent base, TPCM-independent core, Interface-reliant upper	Two layers: User (isolated apps), Kernel (unified management)
Security Requirements	TPCM-based isolation for inherently trusted objects, TCM-based protection for data I/O	Hardware isolation (user/kernel), trusted boot, access control, data encryption, etc.

2.4 Trusted Cryptographic Services of CubeOS

As the secure collaboration system on TPCM, CubeOS provides trusted cryptographic services, including trusted mea-

surement, trusted reporting, and trusted binding. Trusted

TABLE 3
Systematic comparison between ATC/CubeOS and conventional TEE solutions (OP-TEE).

Dimension	ATC with CubeOS	Conventional TEE solutions with OP-TEE
Threat Model Assumptions	Attacker aims to subvert the security collaboration and forge the system's trusted state.	Attacker targets sensitive computation tasks (e.g., enclaves/trusted applications).
Security Objectives	Ensure secure collaboration; verify hosts' trust state.	Protect confidentiality and integrity of sensitive computation tasks.
Execution Model	Event-driven monitoring; dynamic orchestration of security mechanisms.	Static isolation; on-demand execution of trusted applications within special security area.
System Capabilities	Orchestrate multiple security mechanisms; support dynamic policy adaptation.	Provide isolated execution environments, trusted storage, cryptographic services, and remote attestation.
Interface Design	Unified API and configuration interfaces; non-blocking channels.	GlobalPlatform TEE Internal API; TEE Client API; TPM interface.
Deployment Complexity	Requires security mechanism adaptation, understanding of business logic and security requirements.	Requires partitioning application into trusted/untrusted parts and redeveloping trusted parts using the GP API.
Portability and Extensibility	Highly portable; easily extensible with new security mechanisms.	Tightly bound to hardware TEE environment; limited cross-platform interoperability.

measurement establishes the trusted state of the local host. Trusted reporting supplies verifiable evidence of the local host's trusted state to remote hosts. Trusted binding ensures that external data can only be accessed when the local host is in a trusted state. The trustworthiness is anchored in the system's trust roots: the Root of Trust for Measurement (RTM), the Root of Trust for Reporting (RTR), and the Root of Trust for Storage (RTS).

Figure 4(a) illustrates the implementation of trusted measurement in CubeOS. The process combines a static measurement phase (blue area) and a dynamic measurement phase (pink area). In the static measurement phase, trusted boot begins with static measurement mechanism 0 (purple box), which serves as the traditional RTM. A chain of static measure mechanisms is then formed, where each module is measured by its predecessor before measuring its successor. After all boot processes, security mechanisms, and initial policy states are measured, CubeOS collects the measurement values and writes them into Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) in the local host's TCM. These PCRs are reserved for static measurement (referred as static PCRs). The values stored in these registers form tamper-evident logs, providing an undeniable record of the static measurement process.

The dynamic measurement phase comprises a set of security mechanisms that perform system monitoring during runtime. We define the dynamic measurement mechanism 0 (purple box) as a runtime root of trust. Executed within CubeOS, this mechanism is designed to mitigate attacks originating from the computing component. In the ATC architecture, the TPCM operates as a master, enabling it to actively monitor the computing component. Leveraging this capability, dynamic measurement mechanism 0 also performs runtime monitoring of the computing component. Consequently, we propose designating it as a dynamic RTM to serve as a trusted anchor during runtime. Initiating from this dynamic RTM, subsequent dynamic measurement mechanisms establish a measurement chain in the host. During operation, dynamic measurement mechanisms generate event audit logs, and feeds audit digests into CubeOS. CubeOS writes these digests into the PCRs reserved for dynamic measurement (dynamic PCRs). The dynamic PCR

values then serve as the basis for the integrity verification of the stored digest sequence, the audit logs and the dynamic trust state of the local host.

Figure 4(b) illustrates the process of trusted reporting. CubeOS provides a remote host with a trusted measurement report signed by an Attestation Key (AK), which contains verifiable values of the trusted measurement PCRs from the local host's TCM. The remote host uses these PCR values to verify the authenticity of the report. The trustworthiness of the entire process originates from Endorsement key (EK, purple box) serving as RTR in the local host's TCM and the certification by a trusted third party (CA).

The entire process can be divided into three stages. At the first stage, the CA provides its public key certificate to both local and remote hosts and obtains the (EK public key, local host information) tuple through a trusted channel.

At the second stage, the AK certificate generation process (depicted by cyan arrows) is executed. When an AK_Request command issued for TCM, an encrypted AK request blob is generated. Next, the CA decrypts this blob using its private key and verifies the contained certificate information. Upon successful verification, the CA issues an AK certificate signed with its private key, and seals this certificate into an AK active blob using the public EK of TCM in the local host, and then, returns it to TCM. After executing AK_Activate command in TCM, the AK certificate is extracted and installed in CubeOS. The activated AK certificates can be distributed to remote hosts for use in the next stage.

At the third stage, the trusted reporting process is implemented (depicted by light green arrows). In this procedure, the expected values of the trusted measurement PCRs serve as the trust standard. TCM generates a trusted report containing the current trusted measurement PCR values and signed by the AK generated in the previous stage. This report is then submitted to a remote host. The remote host uses the AK public key to verify the report's integrity and compares the reported PCR values with the trusted standards in order to assess the trust state of the local host.

Figure 4(c) illustrates the trusted binding procedure of CubeOS. It enables a remote host to provide data that can only be decrypted and used when the local host is in the

Fig. 4. Trusted Cryptographic Services of CubeOS.

trusted state. The origin of this data protection is the Storage Root Key of the local host's TCM (purple box), serving as the RTS. The trusted binding procedure can be divided into three stages: bindkey transmission phase, session key exchange phase, and data encryption/decryption phase. At the bindkey transmission phase (depicted by cyan arrows), CubeOS first creates an asymmetric bindkey bound to the trusted measurement PCR values and then uses the AK to issue a corresponding key certificate containing the bindkey's public key. This certificate is sent to a remote host, which can subsequently verify both the origin of the bindkey and the specific PCR values bound to it by validating the AK's signature on the certificate.

At the session key exchange phase (depicted by yellow arrows), the remote host first generates a random session

key and encrypts it using the public bindkey. This encrypted session key is then sent to the local host's CubeOS, and only decrypted (unbound) within its TCM using the corresponding bindkey. This operation succeeds only if the current PCR values in the TCM match the expected state.

At the data encryption/decryption phase (depicted by green arrows), the remote host can transmit data encrypted with the session key. Then, having established the trusted binding, the local host can decrypt this protected data. This capability enables precise data usage control through the trusted cryptographic service.

Fig. 5. Adaptation methods of CubeOS to different external security mechanisms.

2.5 Adaptation of CubeOS to different external security mechanisms

CubeOS needs to support the connection between TPCM and different external security mechanisms. There are three types of external security mechanisms: security mechanisms in the computing node, trusted cryptographic mechanisms provided by the local TCM, and trusted collaboration mechanisms provided by the remote TPCM. By using channels and adaptation modules, CubeOS interacts with these mechanisms via standard message input/output interfaces.

Figure 5a shows the adaptation method of CubeOS to the security mechanism in the computing node. We constructed an audit adaptation module to obtain audit information, and a policy adaptation module to output policy information. The audit adaptation module and policy adaptation module are generally used as the starting and ending points of the primary route of security monitoring processes. These two types of modules include a bus channel, which connects security agents embedded in the computing node, and implements format conversion between external data and internal messages in the functions of modules.

TABLE 4
Five development stages of the dynamic collaboration scheme for multiple security mechanisms.

Stage	Appropriate team	Objectives	Outputs	Backtracking criteria
Preparation	Product development team / system integration team	Implement adaptation of CubeOS and external security mechanism	Security agents, adaptation modules of security mechanism	none
Design	Solution design team	Develop the security monitoring requirements specification	security monitoring requirements specification	The selected security mechanisms are incompatible with the defined monitoring requirements
Development	Solution development team	Define the security monitoring modules/routes and the new record formats	New record formats, module binaries & sources, route definitions	Development is blocked by an unresolvable technical issue in the prescribed approach.
Construction & execution	System integration team/security operations team	Implement and run the security monitoring process	Deployed configurations and execution reports	Unresolved operational issues block deployment
Testing & evaluation	Security assessment team	Assess the security monitoring effectiveness	Security assessment plan and security assessment report	Assessment identifies unacceptable security risks

Figure 5b shows the adaptation method of the trusted cryptographic mechanism between CubeOS and TCM device. We implemented a dual layer structure consisting of a TCM device adaptation layer and a TCM function adaptation layer to adapt the trusted cryptographic mechanisms of TCM devices. The TCM device adaptation layer implements the conversion of device channel data to the TCM device messages. The TCM function adaptation layer provides an abstract TCM function message interface externally, while internally maintaining databases of TCM session information and TCM entity information, supporting the conversion between TCM device messages and TCM function messages.

Figure 5c shows the adaptation method of the trusted collaboration between two TPCMs. We constructed the adaptation modules and the network module in CubeOS of the collaboration initiator. Correspondingly, we constructed the network module and the collaboration operation module in CubeOS of the collaboration executor. The initiator generates a collaboration request message via the adaptation module. This message is then transmitted to the executor via the network module. The collaborative task is executed by the collaborative operation module of the executor.

The above three adaptation methods enable security monitoring processes to utilize external security mechanisms in a standardized manner, thus ensuring the compatibility of CubeOS with a variety of such mechanisms.

2.6 A standardized scheme for dynamic collaboration in CubeOS

In CubeOS, we designed a standardized scheme for dynamic collaboration of multiple security mechanisms. This scheme comprises five stages: preparation, design, development, construction & execution, and testing & evaluation. These stages can be independently developed by different technical teams and support backtracking among them.

By default, the five stages are executed sequentially. When the support provided in the previous stage cannot meet the requirements of the next stage, developers should clarify the requirements and trace back to the previous stage. Table 4 presents the conditions suitable for technical teams,

work objectives, output results, and backtracking criteria for different stages.

This scheme features a clear division of labor, and the results of each stage can be represented digitally. Most of the results are reusable, which can effectively reduce the development workload of dynamic collaboration with multiple security mechanisms.

2.7 Formal Analysis of primary security threats to CubeOS

In this section, we analyze the primary security threats to CubeOS. Considering the physical protection of TPCM and TCM devices, the trusted nature of all CubeOS entities, and the difficulty of interfering with the high-speed system bus, we suggest that the primary security threats to CubeOS, as shown in Figure 6.

We delineate the system architecture into a trusted domain (green area) and an untrusted domain (yellow area). The trusted domain encompasses CubeOS, TPCM hardware, the TCM, the system bus between the security component and the computing component, and the static measurement mechanism 0 within the computing component. Conversely, the untrusted domain comprises the communication channel between the TPCM and TCM, as well as the computing component other than the static measurement mechanism 0. Notably, within the computing component, two distinct protection domains are safeguarded by security mechanisms and monitored by CubeOS. The static protection domain (enclosed by a dashed rectangle) contains dynamic measurement mechanisms, security mechanisms, and trusted agents. Security in this domain is governed by predetermined static policies. The dynamic protection domain (enclosed by a dashed ellipse) contains the protected entities of the operating system and applications in the computing component. Its security mechanism is defined by dynamic policies orchestrated by CubeOS. Consequently, potential threats to the system are primarily targeted at these untrusted domains.

Based on the above analysis, in Figure 6, we illustrate three primary security threats with the escalating attacker capabilities.

Fig. 6. The primary security threats to CubeOS.

Threat 1 exploits vulnerabilities within the dynamic protection domain caused by incomplete or delayed policy updates. Executing this attack requires only basic system development and operational proficiency to leverage these policy flaws.

Threat 2 targets vulnerabilities within the static protection domain stemming from inadequate security mechanisms. Executing this attack demands a higher level of sophistication: attackers must not only identify and exploit these flaws but also evade or subvert the trusted measurement process to remain undetected.

Threat 3 targets the communication channel between the TPCM and TCM via side-channel analysis. This scenario presupposes that the attacker has the capability to compromise the host and to perform side-channel attacks to extract TCM keys.

To systematically characterize these threats, we employ Communicating Sequential Processes (CSP) [21] to conduct a detailed analysis in the following subsections.

2.7.1 Analysis of dynamic security collaboration threat

The dynamic protection domain is implemented by security monitoring processes in the system through dynamic policy updates. However, policy updates require a computational process. Before this process completes, a policy mismatch may occur, which creates the attack window for the dynamic security collaboration threat.

We employ CSP to describe the dynamic policy update procedure. First, consider a single security monitoring process M . The events of M include a monitoring event($monitor$), a measurement event($measure$), and a deci-

sion event($decision$). M performs security monitoring based on its current state $state_{curr}$; $monitor$ acquires audit data ($audit$); $measure$ determines a new state($state_{new}$) based on both $audit$ and $state_{curr}$; and $decision$ then generates a policy ($policy$) according to $state_{new}$. The CSP specification for the security monitoring process is given in Equation 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M(state_{curr}) &= monitor?audit \\
 &\rightarrow measure(audit, state_{curr})!state_{new} \\
 &\rightarrow decision(state_{new})!policy \\
 &\rightarrow M(state_{new})
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Multiple monitoring processes in CubeOS are interleaved within the CSP specification. Therefore, their collective behavior can be described by Equation 2:

$$\mathcal{M} = M_1 ||| M_2 ||| \dots ||| M_n \quad (2)$$

The dynamic evolution of the protection domain occurs when the relevant security monitoring processes within the set \mathcal{M} acquire sufficient audit information, accurately assess the system state, and consequently output correct policies based on that accurate state assessment. The time required to complete this process constitutes an exploitable time window for an attacker.

Equation 3 formally describes the attack process A against the dynamic protection domain. A is predicated on existing vulnerability information $vuln_{old}$. The events in A are $probe$, $analysis$, and $attack$. Within a single cycle, the attacker can either: (1) launch $attack$ directly based on $vuln_{old}$, or (2) execute $probe$ to obtain current host information

(*hostinfo*), then perform *analysis* to update vulnerability information to (*vuln_{new}*). In both cases, the cycle concludes by returning to the initial state, with *vuln_{old}* being updated to *vuln_{new}* in case (2) for subsequent cycles.

$$\begin{aligned}
A(vuln_{old}) = & ((attack(vuln_{old}) \rightarrow A(vuln_{old})) \\
& \sqcap (probe!hostinfo \\
& \rightarrow analysis(vuln_{old}, hostinfo)!vuln_{new} \\
& \rightarrow A(vuln_{new}))
\end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The above analysis indicates that an attack launched directly based on existing vulnerability information may suffer from a lower success rate due to the lack of up-to-date system information. Although an attack could be conducted after probing and analysis, the significantly increased time cost may cause the attacker to miss the viable attack window. Correspondingly, CubeOS can address this threat from two perspectives: enhancing the response speed and accuracy of security monitoring to shorten the attack window, and increasing the variability of policy content and combination to reduce the attacker's success probability.

2.7.2 Analysis of trusted measurement procedure threat

According to the CSP formalism, the system's static measurement procedure is modeled as a sequence of events, while the dynamic measurement procedure is represented as a set of processes. Let e_0 denotes the static measurement event performed by the RTM, e_1, \dots, e_m denote the subsequent static measurement events. D_0 denotes the dynamic measurement mechanism 0, a trusted entity within the system whose characteristics are anchored in the TPCM, as illustrated in Figure 4. And D_1, \dots, D_n denote the subsequent dynamic measurement mechanisms of the system. Then, the overall trusted measurement process, \mathcal{M} , is given by Equation 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{M} = e_0 \rightarrow e_1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow e_m \rightarrow \\
(D_0 \parallel D_1 \parallel \dots \parallel D_n)
\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The static measurement mechanism aligns with that of traditional trusted computing. Its trustworthiness primarily depends on the integrity and tamper resistance of the RTM, as well as the integrity of the static chain of trust. Our analysis therefore focuses on the capability of the dynamic trusted measurement process to resist threats.

Serving as the anchor of the dynamic measurement chain, D_0 maintains its trustworthiness and performs measurements on D_1 , as detailed in Section 2.4. The following analysis focuses on the subsequent dynamic measurement processes D_i ($i \geq 1$).

A dynamic measurement process D_i ($i \geq 1$) is defined in Equation 5. It comprises three events: *monitor*, *measure*, and the PCR logging *extend*. The PCR value associated with the process serves as the undeniable record of the trust state. Assume the current PCR value is PCR_{old} . Within an execution cycle, D_i starts with the *monitor* event. If *monitor* detects no system events, the process remains idle for the current cycle. If *monitor* detects an event *event*, the *measure* event is triggered to analyze it. Based on this analysis, the process follows one of the two paths: (1) If *measure* finds no anomaly, the process remains inactive; (2) if a threat

is identified, *measure* outputs an *alert* and *extend* writes the hash of this *alert* into the PCR, updating the state to PCR_{new} .

$$\begin{aligned}
D_i(PCR_{old}) = & ((monitor \rightarrow D_i(PCR_{old})) \\
& \sqcap (monitor!event \rightarrow \\
& ((measure(event) \rightarrow D_i(PCR_{old})) \\
& \sqcap (measure(event)!alert \\
& \rightarrow extend(hash(alert), PCR_{old})!PCR_{new} \\
& \rightarrow D_i(PCR_{new})))
\end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Due to the characteristics of the PCR registers, once the *extend* event is completed, the state of the dynamic measurement process cannot revert to PCR_{old} at runtime. Therefore, when a remote user verifies the trust state of the local node, the local node must submit all *alert* information to justify the generation of PCR_{new} . Consequently, the threat resistance of the dynamic measurement mechanism combines the attack resistance and monitoring capabilities of all the dynamic measurement processes. An attacker can achieve their objective only by either evading detection or subverting the dynamic measurement process before the *extend* operation executes.

Given the chained nature of the dynamic measurement mechanisms and the assured trustworthiness of D_0 , an attacker aiming to subvert D_i must compromise either D_{i-1} or its preceding ancestors in the chain. However, due to system resource constraints, integrity checks by D_{i-1} on D_i are performed periodically rather than continuously. This intermittent monitoring inevitably creates a temporal window of vulnerability for potential attackers.

Based on this analysis, two primary approaches can be applied in CubeOS to defend against threats to the trusted measurement process. First, by migrating computing parts of the dynamic measurement mechanisms into CubeOS, the attack surface can be reduced, thereby enhancing their intrinsic attack resistance. Second, by leveraging the TPCM's computational power, we can enhance the detection of attacks targeting the trusted measurement process, thereby narrowing the attacker's window of opportunity.

2.7.3 Analysis of side-channel attack for the TCM

Side-channel attacks pose a significant threat to the security of keys stored in cryptographic modules such as TPM/TCM [22]. In the context of a TCM, an attacker can infer internal key objects by analyzing side-channel information gathered from carefully orchestrated access patterns. Within the CubeOS security framework, access to the TCM is mediated by CubeOS residing in the TPCM; thus, even a compromised host cannot bypass CubeOS. This architecture enables two main countermeasures for mitigating side-channel threats: physical protection of the TPCM/TPM, and parallelized design of TCM access within CubeOS to obfuscate timing or power channels.

First, we model the TCM invocation process using CSP. Let the key computation process within the TCM be denoted as $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$. When a TCM invocation is executed for a specific key *key*, the invocation command is $cmd(key)$, and the corresponding event set is

$C(key) = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n \mid k_i \in C\}$. The return value is $return(key)$. Thus, the complete TCM invocation process $CALL(key)$ can be described by the event sequence given in Equation 6:

$$\begin{aligned} CALL(key) &= input?cmd(key) \\ &\rightarrow k_1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow k_n \\ &\rightarrow output!return(key) \rightarrow \checkmark \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Assuming each distinct computation step of the command has a corresponding side-channel signal, let $\Sigma = \{k_1.s_1, k_2.s_2, \dots, k_n.s_n\}$ denote the combined set of computation steps and their associated side-channel signals. Then, under the consideration of side-channel information, the trace of $CALL(key)$ is given by Equation 7:

$$\begin{aligned} trace(CALL(key)) &= \langle cmd(key), \\ &k1.s1, k2.s2, \dots, k_n.s_n, \\ &return(key) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equation 8 characterizes the information a side-channel attacker can obtain — including the input and output of the TCM, and the side-channel information trace extracted from the execution trace of $CALL(key)$.

$$\begin{aligned} Sideinfo(CALL(key)) &\triangleq \langle cmd(key), \\ &s1, s2, \dots, s_n, \\ &return(key) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Based on $Sideinfo(CALL(key))$, an attacker can deduce characteristics of the computational process to assist in deciphering the key stored within the TCM.

From the above analysis, it can be deduced that CubeOS could integrate hardware security mechanisms to counter side-channel attacks. Two defensive approaches are available. The first is to encapsulate the TPCM and TCM together for physical protection. In this scenario, the attacker cannot directly access $cmd(key)$ or $return(key)$ and must rely solely on side-channel signals, thereby raising the attack difficulty. Another approach is to modify the TCM to support parallel cryptographic operations. When CubeOS invokes the TCM, each call can be designed to involve multiple TCM accesses, potentially interleaved with random TCM commands. Consequently, within the TCM's execution trace, different computation commands occur in parallel, causing their side-channel features to be superimposed and obfuscated, which significantly complicates side-channel analysis.

2.8 Generality and Portability of CubeOS

In CubeOS, the three-layer architecture ensures the platform independence of the core layer. The unified abstract interface design of the core layer provides generalized functional support for the upper layer. Additionally, its software-defined recording and routing capabilities, along with standardized adaptation methods, allow CubeOS to be deployed across diverse environments. These features demonstrate that CubeOS requires only an isolated environment with adequate computational and memory resources, a data channel to the computing component, and a TCM/TPM interface—requirements that are not exclusive to TPCM.

Consequently, although CubeOS is optimized for TPCM, it is theoretically compatible with other isolation architectures, such as TEE+TPM combinations or any hardware/software environments offering cryptographic support.

However, as mentioned in Section 2.7, TPCM offers two distinct security advantages. First, its independent CPU and operating environment shield CubeOS from underlying attack mechanisms, including CPU vulnerabilities and side-channel attacks. Second, it provides a trusted anchor for the dynamic measurement mechanism. Leveraging these capabilities, CubeOS deployed in a TPCM environment delivers a more comprehensive security assurance solution.

Furthermore, the design philosophy of CubeOS decouples its development from specific hardware mechanisms. This modularity enables the core layer of CubeOS to be designed and implemented independently in a general-purpose operating system environment, serving as a foundation for subsequent upper-layer security solutions. Such an approach facilitates the early validation of CubeOS's feasibility, the performance evaluation of the core layer, and the assessment of its security mechanisms. Upon successful validation, the system can be ported to diverse TPCM environments by integrating a thin hardware abstraction layer as the bottom layer of CubeOS. In the following section, we adopt this approach for the development and validation of CubeOS.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF CUBEOS IN LINUX ENVIRONMENT

This section details the Linux-based implementation of CubeOS and validates its design feasibility. Specifically, Section 3.1 introduces cubeos-1.5 [23], a prototype implemented entirely via software emulation to verify the feasibility of the proposed three-layer architecture. Section 3.2 describes the construction of a TCM emulator testbed, used to conduct a series of performance evaluations on cubeos1.5. In Section 3.3, we validate the system's standardized adaptation approaches by developing modules for diverse external mechanisms. Finally, Section 3.4 presents a case study demonstrating data protection in a typical application, thereby verifying the system's dynamic policy deployment capabilities.

It is important to note that our experimental evaluations were conducted in a fully software-based environment, serving as an early-stage prototype for engineering validation. Since assessing hardware-dependent metrics necessitates physical TPCM support, such evaluations were outside the scope of this study. Specifically, we did not evaluate hardware-accelerated cryptographic performance, actual channel throughput between computing and security components, dynamic measurement chains in practical settings, or physical side-channel resistance. Instead, as a preliminary prototype evaluation, our work focuses primarily on architectural feasibility, system usability, and software-level performance.

3.1 Implementation of cubeos-1.5

Following the design scheme in Figure 3, we developed cubeos-1.5 in a Linux environment as an implementation of CubeOS, which verified the feasibility of the three-layered architecture scheme.

TABLE 5
Implementation of the core layer code of cubeos-1.5.

Code Category	Directory	Description	Source Lines of Code	Binary size(bytes)
Object definition and basic function	cubelib/include	Basic definitions, shared data structures, and internal functions	1715	0
	cubelib/alloc	Memory management	292	16.1k
	cubelib/string	Memory and string manipulation	429	20.1k
	cubelib/json	Json processing	936	25.1k
Object management	cubelib/crypto	Data encoding (Base64) and cryptographic services: symmetric ciphers, hashing	1487	42.1k
	cubelib/struct_deal	Record schema generating and data processing.	4191	82.8k
	cubelib/memdb	In-memory database implementation and operations	1863	51.7k
	cubelib/message	Message schema and operations	2394	53.0k
	cubelib/ex_module	Module implementation and operations	1103	36.5k
	cubelib/channel	Channel implementation and operations	374	20.4k
execution entity	cubelib/route	Route schema and operations	1560	44.8k
	proc/src/sys_plugin	Channel read/write entity and message transmission entity	1571	63.4k
Interface definition	proc/main	Configuration & management entity and module scheduling entity	2194	30.8k
	proc/main/base_define	Configuration data definitions	1396	120.5k
Total	include	Functional API declarations	814	0
	-	-	25611	710.0K

Cubeos-1.5 runs as a Linux process, with the bottom layer including system devices and network drivers, and two libraries of Linux (standard libc library and dynamic module loading library libdl). They provide CPU resources, storage resources, and external data interfaces to the core layer. And there are no specific requirements regarding the Linux kernel version for Cubeos-1.5.

The core layer schedules CPU and storage resources, interacts with external security mechanisms via underlying drivers, and supports the management and operation of basic objects in the upper layer. To satisfy the principle of isolation, the core layer is implemented in standard C without external dependencies, as detailed in Table 5. Furthermore, adhering to the principle of minimization, its functions are strictly confined to the construction and execution of security monitoring processes. These design choices are substantiated by the data in Table 5: a total of 25,611 source lines of code and a binary size of merely 710.0 KB. Such a footprint is characteristic of a small embedded operating system.

In the upper layer, we defined and developed some general records, channels and modules for testing cubeos-1.5 and providing some basic functions. Channels include network channels, TCM device channels, and bus channels (simulated by network connection). Modules include debugging modules, messages input/output modules, adaptation modules, and other types. As examples, Table 6 presents some of the general modules in cubeos-1.5.

The implementation of cubeos-1.5 demonstrates the feasibility of providing a platform-independent core layer with general-purpose interfaces, while adhering to the principle of minimization.

3.2 Performance evaluation of cubeos-1.5.

To evaluate the performance of CubeOS, specific implementation instances are required. Therefore, we developed a TCM emulator (vtcm_emulator) and its accompanying TCM

invocation utilities (vtcm_utils) based on cubeos-1.5 [24], serving as the testbed for our experiments.

As illustrated in Figure 7(a), vtcm_emulator employs a modular architecture that implements core TCM functions (e.g., PCR, key management, authentication) and directs the internal data flow. Its counterpart, vtcm_utils (Figure 7(b)), provides a script-driven interface to automate the sending of TCM command sequences and the processing of returned results. Communication between the two components is established via a shared file channel, enabling fully automated command execution and response handling.

Notably, the emulator supports the concurrent activation of multiple TCM instances. As shown in Figure 7(c), a central command server (vtcm_cmd_server) can coordinate multiple vtcm_utils instances to simultaneously submit commands to separate emulator instances. This design allows us to evaluate the system's performance under concurrent loads and multi-instance scenarios, which is critical for assessing its scalability and robustness in practical deployments.

TABLE 6
General modules in cubeos-1.5.

Module name	Module type	Module function
msg_send	debugging module	Export message from record files
msgrecord_store	input/output module	Persist message records to in-memory database
broadcast	input/output module	Forwards received messages to all CubeOS instances connected to local CubeOS
echo_plugin	debugging module	Returns received messages unaltered
tcp_channel	adaptation module	build connection with remote TPCM via TCP/IP network

We conduct a series of performance tests on cubeos-

1.5, including microbenchmarks, configuration loading performance, scalability, and channel throughput, as detailed below.

3.2.1 Microbenchmark evaluation of cubeos-1.5.

The micro-benchmarking method was as follows: TCM script commands were executed via `vcm_utils`, and during execution, the performance of different core primitives was measured. Tests were conducted on three platforms: AMD Ryzen-based PC (4.7GHz), an ARM 3588 embedded environment, and an ARM 3568 embedded environment.

We evaluate the most frequently executed functions associated with CubeOS's basic objects, including message distribution, record serialization/deserialization, record copying, module switching, and channel read/write. We test their execution speeds, and present the test results in Table 7. Given that in the implementation of cubeos-1.5, the size of data processed by core primitives is limited to 4 KB, the results in Table 7 demonstrate that most core primitives in cubeos-1.5 complete execution within $100 \mu s$, which is sufficient to support high-speed security monitoring workflows.

TABLE 7
Microbenchmarks for core primitives of cubeos-1.5.

Test item	Test environment		
	AMD Ryzen PC (4.7GHz)	ARM 3588 (1.8GHz)	ARM 3568 (2GHz)
Message distribution time	$5.5 \mu s$	$22 \mu s$	$115 \mu s$
Record serialization speed	350.8 MB/s	60.1 MB/s	26.1 MB/s
Record deserialization speed	236.5 MB/s	38.3 MB/s	10.8 MB/s
Record copying speed	73.7 MB/s	16.0 MB/s	6.26 MB/s
Module switching time	$0.31 \mu s$	$0.81 \mu s$	$5.44 \mu s$
Channel read speed	462.7 MB/s	137.0 MB/s	43.43 MB/s
Channel write speed	710.0 MB/s	178.5 MB/s	38.62 MB/s

Cryptographic operations are fundamental to CubeOS. Consequently, our microbenchmarks evaluate the performance of symmetric encryption, asymmetric encryption, and hashing algorithms as specified by Chinese national standards. Specifically, we employ SM4 [25] (with a 128-bit key in Cipher Block Chaining (CBC) mode) for symmetric encryption, SM2 [26] (fixed 256-bit key) for asymmetric operations, and SM3 [27] (256-bit digest) for hashing. These functions are implemented in software across various platforms. To mitigate the impact of SM2's high computational latency on system responsiveness, it is executed in a dedicated thread, whereas SM4 and SM3 run within specific modules. As shown in Table 8, SM4 and SM3 achieve throughput sufficient for high-frequency tasks, while SM2 incurs millisecond-level delays. However, given that SM2 is invoked less frequently in typical scenarios, its impact on the overall performance of cubeos-1.5 is relatively small.

TABLE 8
Performance of cryptographic algorithms.

Test item	Test environment		
	AMD Ryzen PC (4.7GHz)	ARM 3588 (1.8GHz)	ARM 3568 (2GHz)
SM4 encryption speed	23.71 MB/s	5.16 MB/s	1.58 MB/s
SM4 decryption speed	27.98 MB/s	4.84 MB/s	1.18 MB/s
SM3 hash speed	131.60 MB/s	22.9 MB/s	5.84 MB/s
SM2 encryption time (500 bytes plaintext)	9.154 ms	37.9 ms	101 ms
SM2 decryption time (597 bytes ciphertext)	4.80 ms	32.1 ms	51.7 ms

3.2.2 Configuration loading performance evaluation of cubeos-1.5

Cubeos-1.5 currently does not support dynamic configuration updates. Any configuration update requires a restart of the system. Here, we evaluate the restart duration using three instances of gradually increasing complexity: `vcm_cmd_server`, `vcm_utils`, and `vcm_emulator`. Table 9 summarizes the architectural complexity of each instance, and Table 10 presents their configuration loading time on the ARM 3588 platform.

TABLE 9
Architecture complexity of testbed instances.

Complexity Metric	Testbed instances		
	<code>cmd_server</code>	<code>vcm_utils</code>	<code>vcm_emulator</code>
System records	64	64	64
Custom records	7	180	180
Routes	2	2	10
Routing rules	8	7	70
Modules	1	3	11

TABLE 10
Configuration loading time of testbed instances.

Test item	Testbed instances		
	<code>cmd_server</code>	<code>vcm_utils</code>	<code>vcm_emulator</code>
System record format loading time	25.7 ms	20.7 ms	25.4 ms
Custom record format loading time	12.0 ms	57.4 ms	58.8 ms
Route loading time	0.363 ms	0.294 ms	1.28 ms
Module initialization time	0.690 ms	0.663 ms	1.71 ms
Total initialization time	40.5 ms	79.7 ms	88.5 ms

The test results indicate that loading the record format constitutes the most time-consuming phase during cubeos-1.5 configuration loading. Nevertheless, even for instances with complex record formats such as `vcm_emulator` and `vcm_utils`, the initialization time remains below 0.1 seconds, which meets the requirements for non-real-time configuration updates.

Fig. 7. Testbed of cubeos-1.5 Vtcm emulator and vtcemutils.

3.2.3 Scalability evaluation of cubeos-1.5

To assess whether the monitoring data across cubeos-1.5 remains stable and predictable under varying configurations, we conduct scalability tests by adjusting the testbed configurations on an ARM 3588 embedded platform.

First, we measure the execution time of the `pcr_read` command by the `vcm_emulator` instance while varying the number of active TCM command execution routes. The results are shown in Table 11. The tests indicate that changes in the routing configuration have little impact on the command execution speed.

TABLE 11
Execution time of `pcr_read` with varying number of TCM command routes.

	TCM command routes				
	1	2	3	4	5
<code>pcr_read</code> performance speed (μs)	807	787	855	837	834

Second, we measure the execution speed of the `pcr_read` command both in its original form and after adding 1-4 `echo_plugin` modules to `pcr_read` route. The results are presented in Table 12. They indicate that when the modules themselves execute rapidly, increasing their number has slightly effect on the overall command execution speed.

TABLE 12
Execution time of `pcr_read` with varying number of modules in TCM command routes.

	Modules added in TCM command routes				
	0	1	2	3	4
<code>pcr_read</code> performance speed (μs)	833	895	925	962	977

Finally, we evaluate the end-to-end latency of the `pcr_read` command under three different communication paths from the command source to the `vcm_emulator` (as illustrated in Figure 7): 1) direct path from `vcm_utils` to `vcm_emulator`; 2) path involving a single intermediate node (`cmd_server`); and 3) path involving two successive intermediate nodes (`trigger` and `cmd_server`). The measured latencies are presented in Table 13. The results demonstrate that direct communication provides the lowest latency, while the insertion of relay nodes introduces additional delay. However, the incremental latency caused by adding more relay nodes remains relatively small. This confirms that cubeos-1.5 achieves both scalability and stable performance.

TABLE 13
End-to-end latency of `pcr_read` with different communication paths.

	number of intermediate node		
		0	1
End-to-end latency (μs)	803	5268	6478

3.2.4 Control-plane performance evaluation of cubeos-1.5

We evaluate control-plane performance tests by concurrently accessing multiple TCM instances. Specifically, we quantify three key metrics across varying concurrency levels: the average execution time of `pcr_read` commands, peak memory consumption, and the average module traversal time. Table 14 presents the results when the number of concurrent access processes ranges from 1 to 5.

The results demonstrate that the `pcr_read` execution time increases steadily with the number of concurrent processes, reflecting predictable and scalable performance under load. Peak memory consumption remains around 100 MB with a slight increase as concurrency grows, which is acceptable for most embedded systems. The average module traversal time stays below $100 \mu s$, confirming that cubeos-1.5 can efficiently iterate through all modules even under moderate concurrency.

TABLE 14
Control-plane performance metrics under concurrent TCM accesses.

Metric	Number of concurrent processes				
	1	2	3	4	5
Average <code>pcr_read</code> execution time (μs)	670	969	1063	1272	1665
Peak memory consumption (MB)	98	102	105	108	112
Average module traversal time (μs)	52	55	58	62	68

The experiments described above demonstrate that cubeos-1.5 delivers excellent performance. Furthermore, in practical deployments, moderating the execution frequency of monitoring workflows can significantly enhance the system's adaptability to a wide spectrum of TPCM hardware environments.

3.3 Adaptation of cubeos-1.5 to external security mechanisms.

Cubeos-1.5 implements adaptation to three external security mechanisms (Section 2.4). We chose the Linux Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) as an example of security mechanism in the computing node. For testing local TCM adaptation, we validated core cryptographic functions. And we enabled the trusted collaboration with remote TPCMs via a dedicated TCP/IP network adaptation module.

3.3.1 Adaptation of cubeos-1.5 to eBPF security mechanism

EBPF is a powerful Linux kernel technology that enables dynamic security mechanisms [28]–[30]. As an example, we developed an eBPF dynamic security mechanism and implemented adaptation of cubeos-1.5 to this mechanism, as shown in Figure 8.

In the linux operating system, we developed a security mechanism based on eBPF to monitor various service applications. The proposed mechanism comprises two security modules and two eBPF buffers in the kernel space, along with an eBPF security agent in the user space (shadowed with light blue in Figure 8). Among these, `syscall_probe` module collects system call audit logs, and `lsm_control` module enforces security policies. Audit buffer was built

Fig. 8. Adaptation methods of CubeOS to the eBPF security mechanism.

upon the ring_buffer structure of eBPF to transfer audit data, and policy_buffer was built upon a HASH_MAP structure of eBPF to store security policies. EBPF security agent communicates to the bus channel in cubeos-1.5 to establish reliable data paths for transmitting audit logs and security policies.

In cubeos-1.5, we developed eBPF_audit module and eBPF_policy module as adaptation modules (shaded with pink in Figure 8). eBPF_audit module transforms raw audit data into structured audit messages, and eBPF_policy module converts policy messages into policy data for eBPF security agent. In the modules, we used three specific record formats (Table 15) to describe the eBPF-derived data.

TABLE 15
Record formats to describe the eBPF-derived data.

Record type	Record subtype	Usage of records
EBPF_DATA	EVENT	Audit event data of eBPF
	SUBJECT	eBPF subject attributes
	RBAC_POLICY	eBPF file access policy

We evaluate the potential steady-state data-plane overhead when using cubeos-1.5 to support eBPF mechanisms. We develop an eBPF application `ebpf_response`, which implements a simple security monitoring function: upon receiving audit information about file operation and modifies the read-write permissions of this file. Subsequently, we implement the same security monitoring functionality within a cubeos-1.5 module, connected it to the eBPF adaptation framework, and compare the performance of these two implementations. Table 16 compares the audit output rate and policy response speed on an AMD Ryzen-based PC and an ARM 3588 embedded system, indicates that the cubeos-1.5 brings minor overhead for audit and policy response.

3.3.2 Adaptation of cubeos-1.5 to the TCM trusted cryptographic mechanisms

TCM provides cryptographic protection, identity authentication, and other functions tied to the trusted state of the

TABLE 16
Data-plane overhead with eBPF adaptation

Test item	Server (AMD PC)		Edge device (ARM 3588)	
	audit reading	policy writing	audit reading	policy writing
Through eBPF_response program	194 μ s	1177 μ s	341 μ s	5275 μ s
Through eBPF adaptation module	235 μ s	1226 μ s	432 μ s	5543 μ s
overhead introduced by cubeos-1.5	41 μ s	49 μ s	91 μ s	268 μ s

computing node. However, the existing APIs of TCM are very complex [31], [32]. Following the adaptation method shown in Figure 5b, we defined the records of core data structures in TCM and developed various TCM trusted cryptographic function adaptation modules [33], enabling security monitoring processes to drive the trusted cryptographic mechanism with messages. Table 17 lists the adaptation modules for the TCM trusted cryptographic mechanism. The simplified message interface provided by these adaptation modules satisfies the cryptographic library API requirements outlined by Schmuser et al. [34], thereby facilitating easy adoption by developers.

3.3.3 Adaptation of cubeos-1.5 to remote TPCMs

The adaptation method illustrated in Figure 5c requires a network module. For this purpose, the `tcp-channel` module in Table 6 serves as the network module by establishing TCP connection to remote TPCMs and providing services for their registration and location. Remaining adaptation modules in Figure 5c need to be specifically designed according to the remote collaboration requirements.

TABLE 17
Adaptation modules for the TCM trusted cryptographic mechanism.

Module name	Module functions
create_key	Generate TCM keys from attributes
pcr_rw	Read, write and log pcr values
pik_client	Send Platform Identity Key (PIK) request
	Activate PIK and extract its certificate from activation package
pik_casign	Verify PIK request and sign PIK certificate in CA
pik_verify	Remote client PIK certificate verification
tcmkey_bind	Bind data
	Unbind data
tcmkey_sign	Sign data
	Verify data
quote_report	Generate a TCM quote for platform state attestation
	Verify the TCM quote
key_certify	Generate a certificate for a local TCM key, sign it by PIK
	Verify a TCM key certificate

3.4 Implementation of a security assurance scheme based on cubeos-1.5.

In this section, following the scheme outlined in Table 4, we developed a security assurance solution based on cubeos-1.5 for the AI application scenario shown in Figure 9a, to verify CubeOS in supporting dynamic collaboration among multiple security mechanisms.

The scenario depicted in Figure 9a involves a system consisting of an IoT edge device connected to a camera and an AI server. Both the edge device and server are deployed with the Linux operating system and installed cubeos-1.5. The edge device captures facial images through the camera, assembles them into a training set, and sends the set to the server. Utilizing the training set in AI training service, the server generates a trained model, and sends it back to the edge device. Based on this trained model, the edge device performs inference in AI inference service to recognize the individuals captured by the camera. The entire process is controlled by the manager programs in the edge device and the server, which invoke file transfer services and AI services.

This scenario involves separate owners for the edge device and the AI server. To protect the private data of the edge device owner, the security assurance scheme needs to meet the following two security requirements: (1) the training set can only be used for AI training on the server, and cannot be leaked or used for any other purposes; (2) the trained model cannot be leaked or retained on the server.

According to the standardized scheme presented in Table 3, we implemented the security assurance solution through five stages.

At **preparation stage**, we selected the eBPF security mechanism (as shown in Figure 8) and the trusted TCM cryptographic mechanism to support the data security assurance solution. The primary efforts for the adaptation are described in Section 3.3, but the trusted cryptographic mechanism does not provide encryption/decryption support in user space. Thus, we implemented a user-space cipher program that incorporates an adaptation module

in cubeos-1.5 (named key_support). This program requests encryption keys from the key_support module and performs file encryption and decryption. As a result, the adaptation modules prepared in this stage are eBPF_audit and eBPF_policy modules (Figure 8), tcmkey_bind module (Table 15), tcp_channel module (Table 5), and key_support module. These modules are deployed within cubeos-1.5 on both the edge device and the server to adapt to external security mechanisms, as shown in Figure 9b.

At **design stage**, we proposed a solution to achieve “usable but invisible” data by combining dynamic access control strategies with trusted cryptographic mechanisms, as shown in Figure 9b. In the Linux operating system, the AI application is isolated using the eBPF security mechanism on both the edge device and the server, and its data transmissions are protected by cipher programs running on both sides. Based on this solution, we defined ten specific security requirements. These requirements are listed in Table 18 in the expected chronological order of the monitored behaviors.

At **development stage**, we implemented the security monitoring process in two sequential steps: module development and route configuration. Module development involves decomposing the security monitoring requirements and developing corresponding modules for each function. Note that we have already addressed the functions related to external security mechanisms by pre-selecting adaptation modules at preparation stage. For the internal management, we developed new modules listed in Table 19.

Route configuration connects modules in sequence through routes to construct security monitoring processes. By integrating with various external security mechanisms, the monitoring function implemented by the modules in Table 19 satisfy the specific requirements outlined in Table 18. These functions are tagged with their corresponding requirement identifiers, thereby ensuring full traceability. Figure 10 illustrates how the routes achieve these security monitoring processes, in which distinct routes are represented by arrows in different colors.

Figure 10a presents the implementation of security monitoring processes 1.1, 1.2, 1.4, and 1.5 in the edge device through routes. All the monitoring processes in the edge service use edge_ctrl route (blue arrows) as their primary route. The processes 1.1 and 1.4 employ edge_key_get route (pink arrows) as their auxiliary route to provide keys to the cipher program in the Linux operating system of the edge device, and to manage the keys through the in-memory database.

Figure 10b presents the implementation of security monitoring processes 2.1-2.4 in the server through routes. All the monitoring processes in the server employ server_ctrl route (blue arrows) as their primary route. Process 2.1 utilizes edge_key_get route (purple arrows) as an auxiliary route. By integrating modules (bindata_get, meta_get_server, and tcmkey_bind), process 2.1 invokes TCM to retrieve a key from the bound data. The obtained key is then stored and supplied to the cipher program in the Linux operating system for decrypting the training set. Process 2.4 uses server_crypt route (pink arrows) as its auxiliary route to retrieve the key from the in-memory database for encrypting the trained model.

TABLE 18
Security monitoring requirements in the expected chronological order of the monitored events.

Device	Program	Object access	Response decision	Policy objective	Policy content	Identifier
Edge device	Manager program	Generate training set	Generate encryption key and encrypt training set	eBPF agent	Authorization for training set accessing	1.1
				cipher program	encryption key	
	Cipher program	Encrypt training set	Authorize transmission of encrypted training set	eBPF agent	Authorization for encrypted training set transmission	1.2
	Manager program	Send training set	Generate and transmit the training set metadata	cubeos-1.5 in the server	training set metadata	1.3
Server	Manager program	Receive encrypted training set	Authorize encrypted training set accessing	eBPF agent	Authorization for encrypted training set accessing	2.1
	Cipher program	Decrypt training set	Authorize decrypted training set accessing	eBPF agent	Authorization for decrypted training set accessing	2.2
	AI training program	Generate trained model	Retrieve encryption key and encrypt trained model	eBPF agent	Authorization for trained model accessing	2.3
				cipher program	encryption key	
	Cipher program	Encrypt trained model	Authorize transmission of encrypted trained model	eBPF agent	Authorization for encrypted trained module transmission	2.4
Manager program	Send trained model	Generate and transmit trained model metadata	cubeos-1.5 in the edge device	trained model metadata	2.5	
Edge device	Manager program	Receive trained model	Retrieve decryption key and decrypt trained model	eBPF agent	Authorization for encrypted trained model accessing	1.4
				cipher program	decryption key	
	Cipher program	Decrypt trained model	Authorize decrypted trained model accessing	eBPF agent	Authorization for decrypted trained model accessing	1.5

* The number before the decimal point in the identifier represents the device where the monitored object is located (1 for the edge device, 2 for the server), while the number after the decimal point in the identifier represents the expected chronological order of the monitored behavior occurring within the device.

Figure 10c illustrates the implementation of two cross-platform security monitoring processes 1.3 and 2.5. Edge_ctrl (blue arrows) is the primary route of process 1.3, and server_ctrl (orange arrows) is the primary route of process 2.5. Serving as the auxiliary route of process 1.3, edge_meta_gen (pink arrows) generates metadata for the training set at the edge device, invokes TCM via tcmkey_bind module to bind metadata, and transmits the bound data to the server through tcp_channel module. Subsequently, the server receives and stores the bound data for utilization by process 2.1. Similarly, as the auxiliary route of process 2.5, server_meta_gen (purple arrows) generates metadata for the trained model and sends it to the edge device. The metadata is then stored by the meta_rcv_edge module, available for queries by process 1.4.

At **construction and execution stage**, cubeos-1.5 loads the deployment artifacts (module code and configuration) on the edge device and the server, and constructs security monitoring processes. The eBPF security mechanism and cipher program are activated simultaneously. Cubeos-1.5 then orchestrates these security mechanisms to monitor the AI scenario by running security monitoring processes.

At **testing and evaluation stage**, we conducted access control testing thoroughly to verify whether the data assurance solution provided a seamless and transparent data security boundary. First of all, we ran the AI application

to verify that the solution correctly permitted all authorized access requests. Then we performed a series of unauthorized access attempts on the data flow process. These attempts included intercepting the training set from the edge device, unauthorized reading of the training set and the trained model, and attempting to deploy a maliciously modified model on the edge device. The results demonstrated that our solution effectively prevented all unauthorized access attempts while allowing all authorized requests throughout the AI application.

The analysis in Section 2.7.1 indicates that the speed of dynamic policy response directly affects attack window. Accordingly, we have performed macrobenchmark evaluation by measured the execution speed of all the security monitoring process illustrated in Figure 10, using an AMD Ryzen PC as the server side and an ARM 3688 embedded system as the edge device side. The test results are presented in Table 20 and Table 21, respectively.

The test results show that the response time of the security monitoring process does not exceed 20 *ms*. Hence, in the data-protection scenario described in this section, CubeOS leaves attackers only a very narrow time window, which meets common security requirements in typical operational contexts.

The successful implementation of the data assurance solution serves as a successful proof of concept for the pro-

Fig. 9. AI application scenario and its data security assurance solution.

posed standardized scheme. It validates the core capability of cubeos-1.5 to effectively achieve data security assurance by assembling various security mechanisms.

4 RELATED WORK

4.1 Dynamic access control policy researches.

Dynamic access control policy is currently a prominent and active topic in security field, and has attracted widespread attention. Most of the researches followed the technical trajectory of Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA) [35]. Regarding adaptive policy methods, two primary technical approaches are prevalent. One approach advocates for AI-driven continuous authentication and behavioral analysis [36]; however, these studies often lack a thorough assessment of the performance overhead introduced by the AI mechanisms themselves. Another approach emphasizes ensuring policy consistency and correctness through formal verification and

symbolic execution methods [37], while practical and deployable solutions within operational information systems remain lacking.

Currently, the most commonly employed access control mechanisms in ZTA are Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) and Identity and Access Management (IAM) [38]. Nonetheless, a consensus is emerging on the necessity for adaptive policy support within ZTA. Hammar et al. proposed a method for computing security policies that is scalable, offers theoretical guarantees and adapts quickly to changes [39]. However, its practical application is challenged by high computational demands, considerable offline and online computation time and uncertain protective efficacy. Ahmad Salehi S. et al. proposed a scheme utilizing Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) mechanisms to provide support for cross-domain environments [40], while this mechanism lacks the ability to precisely constrain the signer's authority scope and verify subsequent data usage. Bhatt and Sandhu introduced an Attribute-Based Commu-

Fig. 10. Implementation of security monitoring processes in the edge device through routes.

nication Control (ABCC) model within an IoT access control framework [41], but a series of issues remain unresolved from the design phase to concrete implementation. Jayasundara et al. investigated graphical policy configuration tools and automated policy generation frameworks, highlighting that limitations such as lack of flexibility and domain adaptation negatively affect their usability and reliability [42]. The analysis by Ahmadi et al. of two adaptable cyber-defense frameworks, I2NSF and OpenC2, indicates that they are currently more suitable for addressing simple network threats rather than complex and multi-vector attacks [43].

In summary, the field of dynamic security policies lacks a standard model. Many frameworks remain conceptual and lack heterogeneous generality [44]. The integration of new technologies is still largely theoretical or in the pro-

totype stage. Policy enforcement mechanisms often struggle to achieve satisfactory levels of operational feasibility, acceptable performance overhead, and manageable complexity. Conversely, implementable frameworks typically lack scalability and are accompanied by a scarcity of real-world deployments and rigorous performance evaluations in practical validation environments.

4.2 Research in trusted execution environments (TEE)

TEEs are currently the most prevalent hardware-based protection mechanism for computing systems. In recent years, they have been increasingly recognized as a foundational component for building secure systems. Current research generally fall into two main categories.

TABLE 19
The modules developed for the edge device and the server.

Module name	Related Re-quire-ments	Module functions
audit_deal_edge	1.1 - 1.5	Identify the monitored program and its object access behaviors
policy_deal_edge	1.1 - 1.5	Generate access policy from observed program behaviors
key_get_edge	1.1	Generate and store encryption key
	1.4	Extract encryption key from metadata
meta_gen_edge	1.3	Construct key structure for tcmkey_bind module input
	1.3	Generate training set metadata based on tcmkey_bind module output
audit_deal_server	2.1 - 2.5	Identify the monitored program and its object access behaviors
policy_deal_server	2.1 - 2.5	Generate access policy from observed program behaviors
key_get_server	2.1	Extract decryption key from un-binding data
	2.3	Retrieve decryption key from in-memory database
meta_recv_server	1.3	Receive and store training set metadata from the edge device
binddata_get	2.1	Retrieve bound data from metadata stored by meta_recv_server module
meta_gen_server	2.5	Generate metadata for encrypted trained model

(1) Enhancing the adaptability and cross-platform portability of TEE architectures.

To overcome the limitations of platform-specific TEEs like Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone, researchers have proposed architectures targeting greater flexibility and broader applicability. HyperEnclave presents an open and cross-platform process-based TEE, which enables existing SGX programs to execute on commodity AMD servers with minimal modification [45]. Specifically designed for embedded systems, TESLA introduces a TEE architecture that addresses the challenge of running unmodified legacy applications through dynamic mechanisms [46]. In Colony et al. [47], a privileged TEE is designed to allow the trusted computing base to expand securely through capability-based isolation. Aion introduces a configurable TEE architecture for embedded and real-time systems, enforcing deterministic execution and real-time guarantees for dynamically loaded enclaves [48].

(2) Strengthening the intrinsic security of TEE architectures.

Miao et al. explored a general approach to formal analysis by developing a formal functional specification for their proposed compatible TEE architecture, CVTEE [49]. Yin et al. implemented VeriCache, employing formal methods to verify its resilience against cache timing attacks [50]. Huang et al. proposed a TEE hardware architecture that isolates root-of-trust management, ensuring sensitive key remain inaccessible to main TEE processors [51]. To reduce the trusted computing base, Zhao et al. leveraged on-demand paging and Merkle tree protection to shield TEE code and data from board-level physical attacks [52]. Finally, Hunt et al.

integrated TPM-based secure boot with a custom Ultravisor to establish a robust trust chain for confidential computing on the Power ISA, extending TEE concepts beyond x86 and ARM architectures [53].

Despite the aforementioned research in TEEs, traditional TEE-based security architectures still face several inherent limitations. 1) Security solutions based on TEEs lack generality and impose significant development overheads. 2) Existing architectures are constrained by limited adaptability, hindering both the portability of TEE implementations and their collaboration with other security mechanisms. 3) Formal verification efforts typically focus on isolated components rather than the whole system. 4) Trust chains rely primarily on static measurements at boot time, offering limited support for dynamic runtime attestation. These limitations underscore the critical need for a more general-purpose, cross-platform, and flexible security framework.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we designed a general-purpose TPCM operating system CubeOS, guided by four fundamental design principles inspired by the Unix philosophy, and developed cubeos-1.5 as its implementation in the Linux environment. Based on abstract representations of security monitoring processes first proposed in this work, we designed a three-layered architecture for CubeOS, and defined standardized TPCM operating system interfaces consisting of function APIs and configuration data interfaces. These designs decouple the TPCM-hardware-specific components from the rest of the system, thus making CubeOS portable across diverse hardware environments. As the secure collaboration system, CubeOS provides trusted cryptographic services for the entire system. CubeOS provides standardized adaptation methods to connect with external security mechanisms of TPCM, enabling CubeOS to accommodate different security mechanisms. Furthermore, we proposed a standardized scheme for dynamic collaboration of multiple security mechanisms. Additionally, we analyzed the primary security threats to CubeOS by using CSP. Finally, as an implementation of CubeOS, we developed cubeos-1.5 in an isolated and minimalistic manner in the Linux environment, evaluated the performance of cubeos-1.5 by conducting a series of performance tests, and enabled adaptation to external security mechanisms. In an AI application scenario, we demonstrated a verifying example to achieve data security assurance solution by cubeos-1.5. Our study shows that CubeOS can serve as a cross-platform general-purpose TPCM operating system, which is compatible with various security mechanisms and supports standardized data security assurance, thereby guaranteeing secure data circulation and usage in cloud, IoT, big data, and industrial internet scenarios.

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TABLE 20
Execution speed of the security monitoring process in the edge device

	edge_ctrl	edge_key_get	edge_meta_gen	server_meta_gen
performance speed (ms)	6.352	0.832	41.23	0.134

TABLE 21
Execution speed of the security monitoring process in the server

	server_ctrl	server_crypt	binddata_get	server_meta_gen	edge_meta_gen
performance speed (ms)	1.312	0.231	5.635	2.421	0.166

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Yuan and J. Tong, "Attributed based access control (abac) for web services," in *IEEE International Conference on Web Services (ICWS'05)*. IEEE, 2005.
- [2] J. Park and R. Sandhu, "Towards usage control models: beyond traditional access control," in *Proceedings of the seventh ACM symposium on Access control models and technologies*, 2002, pp. 57–64.
- [3] J. Park, R. Sandhu, M. Gupta, and S. Bhatt, "Activity control design principles: Next generation access control for smart and collaborative systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 151 004–151 022, 2021.
- [4] S. Rose, O. Borchert, S. Mitchell, and S. Connelly, "Zero trust architecture," National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), NIST Special Publication 800-207, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-207>
- [5] Q. Zhang and S. Zhao, "A comprehensive formal security analysis and revision of the two-phase key exchange primitive of tpm 2.0," *Computer Networks*, vol. 179, p. 107369, October 2020.
- [6] D. Lee *et al.*, "Keystone: An open framework for architecting trusted execution environments," in *USENIX Annual Technical Conference (ATC)*, 2020, pp. 97–112.
- [7] M. Sabt, M. Achemlal, and A. Bouabdallah, "Trusted execution environment: What it is, and what it is not," in *2015 IEEE Trust-com/BigDataSE/Ispa*, vol. 1. IEEE, 2015, pp. 57–64.
- [8] S. C. Xiang, "Using trusted computing to build cybersecurity," *Qiushi*, no. 20, pp. 33–34, 2015.
- [9] C. X. Shen, "Using active immunity trusted computing 3.0 to build cybersecurity defense line and create a clear cyberspace," *Journal of Information Security Research*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 282–302, 2018.
- [10] J. Hu, C. X. Shen, and B. Gong, *Preliminary Engineering of Trusted Computing 3.0*. People's Posts and Telecommunications Press, 2017.
- [11] S. A. for Market Regulation and S. A. of China, "Information security technology—trusted computing specification—trusted platform control module," State Administration for Market Regulation; Standardization Administration of China, Standard GB/T 40650-2021, 2021.
- [12] S. C. Administration, "Function and interface specification of cryptographic support platform for trusted computing," State Cryptography Administration, Beijing, Standard GM/T 0012-2020, 2020.
- [13] I. J. 1, "Information technology – trusted platform module library – part 1: Architecture," 2015, identical national adoption: INCITS/ISO/IEC 11889-1:2015 (R2024). [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/66510.html>
- [14] S. A. for Market Regulation and S. A. of China, "Information security technology—trusted computing specification—trusted software base," State Administration for Market Regulation; Standardization Administration of China, Beijing, Standard GB/T 37935-2019, 2019.
- [15] N. T. Inc. (2022) Nationz z32h330tc trusted cryptography module chip datasheet. Accessed: 2025-09-06.
- [16] J. Huang, J. Zhang, C. Shen, and J. Zhang, "Dual system trusted terminal computing architecture based on tpcm rot," *Journal on Communications*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 1–14, 2025.
- [17] Z. T. C. I. Alliance, "Technical specification for bmc-based tpcm," Zhongguancun Trusted Computing Industry Alliance, Beijing, Standard T/ZTCIA 005-2025, 2025.
- [18] W. Hou, H. Luo, and Y. Fu, "Design and implementation of hardware trusted platform scheme based on hygon cpu," *Journal of Information Security Research*, vol. 8, no. E2, pp. 43–47, 2022.
- [19] Y. Sun, "Research and application of trusted software base technology," *Journal of Information Security Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 316–322, 2017.
- [20] E. S. Raymond, *Art of UNIX Programming, The, Portable Documents*. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2003.
- [21] P. Y. A. Ryan and S. A. Schneider, *Modelling and analysis of security protocols*. Addison-Wesley-Longman, 2001.
- [22] D. Moghimi, B. Sunar, T. Eisenbarth, and N. Heninger, "TPM-FAIL: TPM meets Timing and Lattice Attacks," in *29th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 20)*. USENIX Association, Aug. 2020, pp. 2057–2073. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity20/presentation/moghimi>
- [23] J. Hu, "cubeos-1.5: An implementation of cubeos in linux," Source code, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gitee.com/biparadox/cubeos-1.5>
- [24] —, "cube-emu-tcm-1.0: Virtual tcm emulator build by cubeos," Source code, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gitee.com/tclab/cube-emu-tcm-1.0>
- [25] Standardization Administration of China, "Information security technology – sm4 block cipher algorithm," Standardization Administration of China, Chinese National Standard GB/T 32907-2016, 2016.
- [26] S. A. of China, "Information security technology – sm2 elliptic curve public key cryptographic algorithm – part 1: General," Standardization Administration of China, Chinese National Standard GB/T 32918.1-2016, 2016.
- [27] —, "Information security technology – sm3 cryptographic hash algorithm," Standardization Administration of China, Chinese National Standard GB/T 32905-2016, 2016.
- [28] LLVM Project. (2022) The extended berkeley packet filter (ebpf) backend. Accessed: 2025-09-23. [Online]. Available: <http://llvm.org/docs/CodeGenerator.html#the-extended-berkeley-packet-filter-ebpf-backend>
- [29] W. Findlay, A. Somayaji, and D. Barrera, "Bpfbbox: Simple precise process confinement with ebpf," in *Proceedings of the 2020 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Cloud Computing Security Workshop*, 2020, pp. 91–103.
- [30] Z. Wang, Y. Guo, B. Zhong, Y. Chen, and Q. Zeng, "Dynamic mitigation mechanism for kernel heap vulnerabilities based on ebpf," *Journal of Software*, vol. 35, no. 7, pp. 3332–3354, 2024.
- [31] Trusted Computing Group, *Trusted Platform Module Library Part 1: Architecture, Level 00 Revision 01.59*, Trusted Computing Group, Nov 2019, version 1.59.
- [32] J. Hu and J. Zhou, "Comparative study on access mechanisms of trusted cryptography module," *Journal of Information Security Research*, vol. 8, no. E2, pp. 105–109, 2022.
- [33] J. Hu, "cube-tcmplugin: Adaption modules of cubeos to tcm device," Source code, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://gitee.com/biparadox/cube_tcmplugin
- [34] J. Schmäser, P. Klostermeyer, K. Friedrich, and S. Fahl, "i'm pretty expert and i still screw it up": Qualitative insights into experiences and challenges of designing and implementing cryptographic library apis," in *2025 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2025, pp. 2322–2340.
- [35] K. Denzel, "A survey of security in zero trust network architectures," 2025.

- [36] A. I. Weinberg and K. Cohen, "Zero trust implementation in the emerging technologies era: Survey," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.09575*, 2024.
- [37] A. M. Ahmadian and M. Balliu, "Dynamic policies revisited," in *2022 IEEE 7th European Symposium on Security and Privacy (EuroS&P)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 448–466.
- [38] C. Manzano, G. Márquez, and H. Astudillo, "Security mechanisms used in systems based on zero trust architecture: A systematic mapping," in *2024 L Latin American Computer Conference (CLEI)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–10.
- [39] K. Hammar, Y. Li, T. Alpcan, E. C. Lupu, and D. Bertsekas, "Adaptive network security policies via belief aggregation and rollout," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.15163*, 2025.
- [40] A. S. S., R. Han, C. Rudolph, and M. Grobler, "DACP: enforcing a dynamic access control policy in cross-domain environments," *Comput. Networks*, vol. 237, p. 110049, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2023.110049>
- [41] S. Bhatt and R. Sandhu, "Abac-cc: Attribute-based access control and communication control for internet of things," in *Proceedings of the 25th ACM Symposium on Access Control Models and Technologies*, 2020, pp. 203–212.
- [42] S. H. Jayasundara, N. A. Gamagedara Arachchilage, and G. Russello, "Sok: Access control policy generation from high-level natural language requirements," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 1–37, 2024.
- [43] C. Ahmadi and J.-L. Chen, "Survey on reinforcement learning techniques for enhancing security and efficiency in zero trust networks," in *2024 10th International Conference on Applied System Innovation (ICASI)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 427–429.
- [44] K. Qu, M. Zhao, and S. Cui, "Zero trust security in modern networks: A survey of applications, challenges, and future directions," in *2025 IEEE 8th Advanced Information Technology, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IAEAC)*, vol. 8. IEEE, 2025, pp. 209–214.
- [45] Y. Jia, S. Liu, W. Wang, Y. Chen, Z. Zhai, S. Yan, and Z. He, "Hyperenclave: An open and cross-platform trusted execution environment," in *Proceedings of the 2022 USENIX Annual Technical Conference*, 2022, p. to appear, arXiv:2212.04197.
- [46] S. F. Allaqband, A. Brahma, S. Krishnan, A. Menon, and C. Rebeiro, "Tesla: Trusted execution support for legacy embedded applications," *IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems*, vol. 2025, no. 4, pp. 899–924, 2025.
- [47] Y. Xia, Z. Hua, Y. Yu, J. Gu, H. Chen, B. Zang, and H. Guan, "Colony: A privileged trusted execution environment with extensibility," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 1–14, 2022.
- [48] F. Alder, J. V. Bulck, F. Piessens, and J. T. Mühlberg, "Aion: Enabling open systems through strong availability guarantees for enclaves," in *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:244077729>
- [49] X. Miao, R. Chang, J. Zhao, Y. Zhao, S. Cao, T. Wei, L. Jiang, and K. Ren, "Cvtee: A compatible verified tee architecture with enhanced security," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 2023.
- [50] L. Yin, H. Wang, Y. Lyu, and D. Wang, "Vericache: Formally verified fine-grained partitioned cache for side-channel-secure enclaves," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 2025.
- [51] T.-T. Hoang, C. Duran, R. Serrano, M. Sarmiento, K.-D. Nguyen, A. Tsukamoto, K. Suzuki, and C.-K. Pham, "Trusted execution environment hardware by isolated heterogeneous architecture for key scheduling," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, p. to appear, 2022.
- [52] S. Zhao, Q. Zhang, Y. Qin, W. Feng, and D. Feng, "Minimal kernel: An operating system architecture for tee to resist board level physical attacks," in *International Symposium on Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:202739351>
- [53] G. D. H. Hunt, R. Pai, M. V. Le, H. Jamjoom, S. Bhattiprolu, R. Boivie, L. Dufour, B. Frey, M. Kapur, K. A. Goldman *et al.*, "Confidential computing for openpower," in *Proceedings of the Sixteenth European Conference on Computer Systems (EuroSys)*, 2021, pp. 294–310.

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